

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL, ECONOMIC AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE FACTORS ON PERCEPTIONS OF ACADEMIC SERVICE SATISFACTION ON NURSING VOCATIONAL CAMPUS

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Abstract

Academic services are essential components in nursing vocational education that must be continuously improved in quality. Social, economic, and demographic factors, as well as Emotional Intelligence (EI), are considered to contribute to achieving a higher level of performance. The purpose of this study is to describe the relationship specific to nursing vocational education institutions. This cross-sectional study was conducted on students of the third diploma nursing program and undergraduates who applied to nurse. The sampling technique used is consecutive sampling. Using respondents' demographic data, the student service satisfaction questionnaire was adopted from the accreditation instrument for higher education in Indonesia. Data analysis used the SMART PLS version 4.0 structural equation modelling and Jamovi. Structural equation modelling analysis shows that social, economic & emotional intelligence factors have a relationship in determining the perception of academic service satisfaction with a p-value of 0.000. Our findings contribute to the literature by showing that social, economic, demographic, and intelligence factors strongly influence perceptions of academic service quality in nursing vocational colleges. Future research should extend the analysis to various sociodemographic, macroeconomic, and geographical variables to gain insight into all the factors that might influence academic service satisfaction to inform policymakers and ensure a higher quality of academic services and, in turn, better academic performance.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Academic Service, Nursing, Vocational, Satisfaction, University, Quality

INTRODUCTION

At first, the concept of quality was often applied to the business world, but recently the world of education has become interested in applying it. The strategy developed using a quality management strategy is to position the world of education as a service institution or, in other words, into a service industry (Christianingsih, 2016). Higher education, as one part of the national education system that is engaged in providing education services, must be able to respond to environmental changes caused, among others, due to increased knowledge of the community as customers (customers), which is indicated by changes in attitudes that are increasingly critical, increasing competition, demands for the world of work that are increasingly demanding. Increasingly high and rapidly changing technology. Service is a process of providing services (service delivery) from service providers to customers (customers). Service quality cannot be judged from the producer's perspective but must move from the customer's perspective, namely customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is a reflection of quality service (Azan, 2015).

Nursing colleges are institutions that have a strategic role and position in achieving the goals of nursing education. Nursing colleges are higher education institutions that produce graduates who are experts in nursing to answer the health needs of the community, nation, and state. Nursing Vocational Education is a diploma education according to the level to have expertise in applied nursing science that is recognized by the government of the Republic of Indonesia.

Service is one of the essential components of education that must be improved continuously. Academic services obtained by students at vocational nursing colleges can be in the form of information services, facilities and infrastructure services, administrative services, academic services, interest talent development services, and skills and welfare services. Services with a characteristic quality (quality nice) are called excellent service. Good quality characteristics include the ease, speed, accuracy, reliability, and empathy of service personnel in providing and delivering services to customers that have a strong impression that customers can immediately feel at that time and at that time. Student satisfaction will be achieved if there is a match between the services provided and student expectations. Student satisfaction is a student's positive attitude toward the services of higher education institutions because there is a match between the service's expectations and the reality they receive. Factors that affect customer satisfaction (Hanan & Karp, 1989) are divided into eight attributes forming customer satisfaction known as "The Big Eight," which consists of Value to Price Relationship, Product Quality, Product Features, Reliability, Warranty, Response to, and Remedy of Problems, Sales experience and Convenience of Acquisition. These factors can be categorized into three categories. Namely, factors related to the product (product quality, the relationship between product value and price, product form, and product reliability according to customer requirements), factors related to service (including assurance and response as well as ways of solving problems), and factors related to experience (including employee experience and convenience and comfort). One factor influencing customer satisfaction is the perception of service performance, which is an assessment given by consumers on service excellence. Perception of service performance is a comparison of consumer expectations of service with the reality or experience consumers get from the service. Whether or not service performance is reasonable depends on the ability of employees to consistently meet consumer needs and expectations (Elmas et al., 2019).

Perception is influenced by socioeconomic status. According to research (Firmiana et al., 2016), Socio-Economic Status significantly affects perceptions. In several studies, emotional intelligence has a relationship with perceptions, especially in adolescence which is the focus of this study (Calero et al., 2018; Jiménez & Lopez-Zafra, 2011; Suhartati & Indrawati, 2017; Vaquero-Diego et al., 2020). Based on the above review and literature study, it was found that socioeconomic status and emotional intelligence are indirectly related to service satisfaction, namely through perception. However, no research discusses the direct relationship between socioeconomic factors and emotional intelligence on satisfaction. So the purpose of this study will be to describe the relationship devoted to nursing Vocational education institutions

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a descriptive study with a cross-sectional approach. This study's sample was all active nursing department students consisting of three nursing diploma study program students, and undergraduate applied nursing at the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health, Sorong, West Papua, and Indonesia. The sampling technique used is consecutive sampling which recruits respondents based on their participation in the survey. This survey uses three questionnaires as research tools: respondent demographic data and a student service satisfaction questionnaire adopted from the university accreditation instrument in Indonesia version 3.0 (BAN-PT, 2019). While the emotional intelligence instrument was adopted (Feldman, 1999; Sterrett, 2000). Demographic data assessed in this study included gender, age, length of time as a student, type of study program, ethnicity, marital status, religion, education level of father and mother, family income class, residence, housing type, working experience, current employment status, the life status of the parents. Emotional intelligence consists of 20 statements that are answered on a scale of never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), usually (4), and always (5). Questions number 1, 5, 9, 12, and 15 are included in the category of self-awareness; statements numbered 3, 6, 10, 13, and 18 are statements that assess self-management. Statements 4, 7, 14, 17, and 19 assessed social awareness, while the relationship management assessment was assessed with 2, 8, 11, 16, and 20. Satisfaction with academic management services consisted of 15 statements with yes and no choices. This statement assesses reliability, ability, speed and responsiveness, service according to provisions, care and attention of lecturers, education staff, and study program managers in serving students, as well as adequacy, accessibility, quality, and cleanliness of facilities and infrastructure. This research was conducted online using the google form application (Google, 2022; Mustamu, 2022), which was distributed via social media WhatsApp (WhatsApp LLC, 2022). Data analysis used the SMART PLS structural equation modeling version 4.0 (SmartPLS GmbH, 2022) and Jamovi (Jamovi, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Result:

The 15 demographic items assessed in this study include gender, study program and years on campus, race, and religion, marital status, education level of father and mother, housing status, residence, employment, monthly household income, and parents' life status, as shown. They are presented in table 1. Based on the analysis, it found that the respondents in this study were dominated by the female gender (85%) who came from the Bachelor of Applied Nursing study program (60.6%) and had been on campus for two years (51.5%). As many as 60.1% of these respondents are non-Papuan races who are Protestant Christians (52.8%). As many as 98.4% of respondents are pure students with no previous work experience (88.1%) but have a monthly income of more than the minimum wage (71%). 46.1% and 45.1% of respondents have a father

who has senior high school education. As many as 86% of respondents have a father and mother who are still alive, so they live together (47.7%) at home (67.9%).

Table 1: Socio-Eco demographic data of respondents

	Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
D1	Age (mean, SD)	19.3 (1.67)	
D2	Gender		
	Male	164	85
	female	29	15
D3	Year at nursing school		
	1st year	83	43
	2nd year	99	51.3
	3rd year	11	5.7
D4	Study program		
	Diploma	76	39.4
	Bachelor of Applied Nursing	117	60.6
D5	Race/ethnicity		
	non Papua	116	60.1
	Papua	77	39.9
D6	Marital status		
	Single	191	99
	Married	2	1
D7	Religion		
	Muslim	87	45.1
	Christian	102	52.8
	Catholic	4	2.1
D8	Father's education level		
	No school	3	1.6
	Elementary school	27	14
	Junior high school	29	15
	Senior high school	89	46.1
	University	45	23.3
D9	Mother's education level		
	No school	8	4.1
	Elementary school	39	20.2
	Junior high school	34	17.6
	Senior high school	87	45.1
	University	25	13
D10	Housing status		
	Alone	41	21.2
	With cousin	35	18.1
	With brothers and sisters	22	11.4
	With parents	92	47.7
	With grandparents	3	1.6
D11			

	Residence		
	Boarding House	62	32.1
	Home	131	67.9
D12	Working experience		
	never	170	88.1
	Worked	23	11.9
D13	Employment		
	Student	190	98.4
	Students and employees	3	1.6
D14	Monthly household income		
	More than minimum wage	137	71
	Less than minimum wage	56	29
D15	Parent's life status		
	Father has died	16	8.3
	Parents are still alive	166	86
	Father and mother have died	6	3.1
	Mother Has died	5	2.6

Table 2 shows that almost all the average components of emotional intelligence are low. Only self-management had good scores (18). The data are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Emotional intelligence

	Emotional Intelligence (mean, SD)	Frequency (n)
EI1	Self-awareness	16.3 (0.15)
EI2	Self-management	18 (3.39)
EI3	Social awareness	16.9(0.17)
EI4	Relationship management	17.2 (3.47)

Table 3: Perceptions of academic service satisfaction

	Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
S1	Reliable and capable lecturer		
	No	6	3.1
	Yes	187	96.9
S2	Fast and responsive lecturer		
	No	10	5.2
	Yes	183	94.8
S3	Certainty according to the rules of lecturer service		
	No	12	6.2
	Yes	181	93.8
S4	Care and attention of lecturers		
	No	11	5.7
	Yes	182	94.3
S5	Reliable and capable education staff		
	No	12	6.2
	Yes	181	93.8

S6	Fast and responsive education staff		
	No	12	6.2
	Yes	181	93.8
S7	Certainty according to the rules of education staff service		
	No	9	4.7
	Yes	184	95.3
S8	Care and attention of education staff		
	No	9	4.7
	Yes	184	95.3
S9	Reliable and capable study program manager		
	No	13	6.7
	Yes	180	93.3
S10	Fast and responsive study program manager		
	No	15	7.8
	Yes	178	92.2
S11	Certainty according to the rules of study program manager service		
	No	14	7.3
	Yes	179	92.7
S12	Care and attention of study program manager		
	No	12	6.2
	Yes	181	93.8
S13	Facilities and infrastructure to support the learning process		
	No	21	10.9
	Yes	172	89.1
S14	Accessibility of facilities and infrastructure		
	No	21	10.9
	Yes	172	89.1
S15	Quality of facilities and infrastructure		
	No	20	10.4
	Yes	173	89.6

The table above found that all respondents perceive lecturers, academic staff, and study program managers as Reliable and capable, fast, and responsive, Certainty according to the rules, Care, and attentive in providing services to students. In addition, Facilities and infrastructure support the learning process; the quality is in good condition and can be accessed during the learning process

Figure 1: The relationship between social, economic & emotional intelligence factors on perceptions of Academy service satisfaction

Structural equation modeling analysis shows that social, economic & emotional intelligence factors have a relationship in determining the perception of academic service satisfaction with a p-value of 0.000.

DISCUSSION

Universities, as education providers, need to provide appropriate academic services to their students. Obtaining quality academic services has become a student's right. Perceptions of the service quality of staff, lecturers, and university facilities are shared. The availability of educational facilities and good management is a critical factor in improving the quality of academic services (Ali et al., 2020).

Nursing education is no longer a vocational education but aims to produce nursing staff who master nursing science and carry out nursing professionally in the community. The higher the level of education, the easier it is to accept and develop knowledge and technology to increase productivity, ultimately improving the quality of nursing services for the community through the arrangement and procurement of a continuing education system. In essence, Nursing Education is an institution that has a significant role in developing and creating a professionalization process for nursing staff. Nursing education can provide the form and style of energy which in turn has a level of ability and can facilitate the formation of the nursing community in providing a voice and contribution to the profession and society.

Nursing education services play an essential role in developing and improving the quality of nurses. However, interest and attention to the quality of nursing education services have only grown in the last decade. The success of nursing education services is determined by providing quality services to the users of these nursing education services (students and the community).

For students to get what is expected, the nursing college must synergize between student expectations and the organization's vision, mission, and goals. The synergy of student expectations and the interests of higher education will be achieved if the academic services carried out prioritize aspects of quality, adequate facilities, and professional management.

Previous research has made an excellent contribution to the field of customer satisfaction. Many studies have determined that high levels of service quality led to high levels of customer satisfaction. Higher education institutions (PT) increasingly focus on student satisfaction during fierce competition. Further support is provided by various studies showing that the main customers of the higher education segment are students, as they are involved in the selection and purchase of services. Therefore, student satisfaction is significant because service quality is the only performance indicator for higher education service providers (Sohail & Hasan, 2021).

The results of our study indicate that social, economic, and demographic factors affect perceptions of academic service satisfaction. Socio-economic status and demographics referred to in this study are gender, age, length of time as a student, type of study program, ethnicity, marital status, religion, education level of father and mother, family income class, residence, housing type, working experience, current status job, life status of parents. A study conducted by (Cagriota, 2007) on 118,000 people living in 81 different countries showed that between 1995 and 2000, gender, age, marital status, occupation, and GDP per capita hurt welfare. However (Frey & Stutzer, 2005) found a positive linear relationship between education and satisfaction level when controlling for income. Knowledge and education increase self-esteem, confidence, hope, and opportunity. Therefore, it leads to higher satisfaction. Our study's results align with research (MIRZAGOLI & MEMARIAN, 2015), which found that the most significant influence on customer satisfaction was residence status, occupation, gender, education, and marital status.

The results of our study indicate that emotional intelligence has a vital role in determining perceptions of the quality of academic services on vocational nursing campuses. These results are in line with the results of research (Parasuraman et al., 1985) showing that EI is related to perceptions of service quality. In addition, service providers must have high EI to feel the customer experience and be adaptive to design and implement services to improve perceptions of service quality (Miao et al., 2017).

This study found several exciting things related to perceiving the quality of academic services, one of which is race. In this study, we found that race is also one of the determinants of the

interpretation of academic service satisfaction. Racism is defined as "a system of structuring opportunities and assigning values based on social interpretations of how a person looks (i.e., race) that harms some individuals and communities, unfairly benefits other individuals and communities, and undermines the power of the whole society through the waste of resources human resources (Mpofu, 2022).

Experiences of racial discrimination are associated with poor mental health (e.g., anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem), health risk behaviors, and reduced social and adaptive functioning, including access to academic services and campus facilities to support the learning process. If this continues, it will affect all aspects of emotional intelligence resulting in the perception of satisfaction. Racial discrimination in education contributes to racial differences in academic achievement and educational attainment, which are important markers of long-term outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Our findings contribute to the literature by showing that social, economic, demographic, and intelligence factors strongly influence perceptions of academic service quality in nursing vocational colleges. Future research should extend the analysis to various sociodemographic, macroeconomic, and geographical variables to gain insight into all the factors that might influence academic service satisfaction to inform policymakers and ensure a higher quality of educational services and, in turn, better academic performance. Clear measures to promote awareness and reduce racism in schools are essential because there is a relationship between satisfaction, emotional intelligence, and perceived racism among students. Despite the benefits of school-based anti-racism interventions, these measures are rarely implemented in schools due to many factors, including political and social variables. Educational materials and information campaigns may require tailored messaging and messaging strategies for different patient population groups and efforts to improve college skills in helping students assess wisely. We must ensure that the entire academic community is equipped and skilled in providing the services that students need based on all backgrounds, which ultimately enhances the equality and quality of educational services for all.

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Footnotes

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